

Seed bank dynamics and the role of mutualisms in the early-life ecology of emerging alien invasive plants: *Acacia paradoxa* in South Africa

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ABSTRACT

Seed banks provide a persistent source of propagules for recruitment and establishment and are a very important factor for the success in recruitment, persistence and spread of many invasive alien plants worldwide. Where eradication of an invasive plant species is deemed feasible, the depletion of its seed bank is a crucial goal. The study of seed bank dynamics (in particular seed density, viability, longevity, and germinability) is a vital component of the quantification of invasion risks and of guidelines to direct eradication programmes. In this study the seed bank dynamics of *Acacia paradoxa*, an invasive alien tree from Australia, targeted for eradication on Table Mountain, South Africa, was investigated. Seed densities in the soil were as high as 3,567 seeds/m². Seed viability was very high (97%) and there was no evidence of a decline in viability of seeds with increasing age. Natural germinability was very low (7%), but this is greatly enhanced by germination triggers such as heat (98% at 100 °C, 35% at 60 °C) and smoke (82%). Seed bank depletion, in burnt areas after the 2009 large and intense fire, ranged from 64.3% to 100% while natural germination depleted seed banks with 3% to 12%. The fire stimulated dense seedling recruitment (236 seedlings/m²), and the density of *A. paradoxa* seedlings was significantly negatively correlated with the density and number of species of taxa plant taxa ($p = 0.036$ and 0.032 , respectively). Implications of these results for the eradication effort include the following: 1) the species has a very large seed bank, and seeds are stimulated to germinate by fynbos fires; 2) prescribed fires can be used to reduce the size of the seed bank; 3) all control operations need to be carefully co-ordinated with fires; and 4) all seedlings must be removed before they reach reproductive age. The role of mutualisms has been determined. DNA sequencing of the intergenic spacer (IGS) region of bacterial symbionts isolated from the plant identified the bacteria associated with the roots of *A. paradoxa* as taxa in the genus *Bradyrhizobium* and *Rhizobium leguminosarum viciae*, both of which are known symbionts of Australian acacias in their native ranges. Experiments in the greenhouse showed that the bacterial strains form effective nodules. Nodulation significantly increased plant biomass ($P = 0.0003$). These results show that *A. paradoxa* benefits from its association with these bacteria, but it remains to be tested how this relationship affects the competitiveness of the species in its new range.

INTRODUCTION

Invasive plant species are a major concern in many parts of the world because of the threat they pose to biodiversity, and the high financial costs of management, among other reasons (Sakai et al., 2001). The best approach for managing plant invasions is to prevent introductions in the first place. Once alien plants are already established and naturalized or invasive, it is best to initiate management early, before the species has reached the phase of exponential growth. In some cases, effective intervention at this stage can lead to eradication.

There are a number of reasons why some plant species become invaders; these relate both to the features of the invaders and of the habitat being invaded (Richardson and Pysek, 2006). Of the attributes of invaders, Rejmanek and Richardson (1996) mention, with reference to pines: the capability to naturally regenerate, short juvenile period, small seed mass, average longevity and fire tolerance. This syndrome of features also confers invasiveness in other woody plants (Rejmanek et al. 2005). One other success strategy for invasive plant species is the maintenance of large, persistent stores of viable seeds in the soil (Richardson and Kluge, 2008), a sure way of persisting after fire (Page, 2006). The role of the seed bank should become more pronounced where a given species has a short juvenile period because such a short juvenile period ensures early reproduction and rapid population growth (Richardson and Pysek, 2006). The production of small-sized seeds is yet another prominent attribute of invasive plants species. Small seeds are associated with the production of large numbers of seeds, better dispersal, high germinability, short chilling period to overcome dormancy, and higher relative growth rates (Rejmanek and Richardson, 1996), all of which puts an invasive species at an advantage compared to natives. Richardson and Kluge (2008) note the production of immense numbers of seeds, and fast growth rates, as some important reasons for the success of Australian *Acacia* species as invaders. Longevity of both standing vegetation and seeds is also crucial for plant invaders. Most Australian *Acacia* spp. they have seed banks that can persist for at least 50 years (Richardson and Kluge, 2008).

As regards the invaded ecosystem, its ability to provide appropriate and effective symbionts with which the invader can form mutualisms can help to support the invader. The role of mutualistic interactions between alien plants establish and indigenous biota has thus been recognised as yet another attribute that has enabled alien plants establish and invade new ecosystems (Richardson et al., 2000).

One such mutualism involves nitrogen-fixing bacteria, *Rhizobia*, and plants, and is common in the family Fabaceae (the legumes). While many species in this family have been purposefully dispersed to novel habitats by man due to their uses as food, fuel wood and in agro-forestry, (Richardson et al., 2000), their capacity to form beneficial mutualisms has played a role in them becoming invasive. How this happens has been the subject of research recently considering that such intimate plant-microbial relationships presuppose a shared evolutionary history (Mondor and Addicot, 2007) and alien plants hardly get into novel habitats together with their co-evolved symbionts (Parker, 2006).

To understand how *Rhizobia* influence invasiveness of alien plants, it is vital to know how seedling growth is influenced by access to *rhizobia* and how this further translates into seedling persistence and consequent plant population spread as these parameters have a bearing on invasion success (Parker 2006). In the case of *Acacia paradoxa* in South Africa, such a determination has not been done as yet.

Acacia paradoxa, an Australian tree, is an emerging invader in South Africa (Nel, et al., 2004) and is classified as a category 1 invader (Conservation of Agricultural Resources Act). This means it cannot be grown and must be eradicated. The species is still confined to the slopes of Devil's Peak in Table Mountain National Park in the Western Cape Province (Zenni et al. 2009). Zenni et al. (2009) did an initial study of this species at this site; they provided a detailed map of the species, and undertook a preliminary assessment of the ecology of the species. They highlighted the need for further information on the seed-bank dynamics of the species for defining a sound management strategy. Zenni et al. (2009) also pointed out the relevance of evaluating habitat suitability of the invaders' new environment for management.

Efforts to eradicate A. Paradoxa

Clearing of invasive plant species in South Africa including Table Mountain has been undertaken as part of the Working for Water (WfW) project which was launched nationally in 1995. These clearing operations are initiatives by Early Detection and Rapid Response (EDRR) programme – a joint programme of WfW and South African National Biodiversity Institute (SANBI). The EDRR programme aims at protecting South African ecosystems from the negative impacts of invasive plants through early detection and necessary rapid response, before detected invasion are out of control. A year later it was noted that there was a decline in the number of plants found after a clearing operations.

But the dimensions of the seed bank, mainly found below canopies of mature trees (Zenni et al., 2009), was yet to be fully determined. These clearing operations reduced the seed rain considering that plants were being removed even before they reproduced. This prevented further additions to the seed bank that existed

The 2009 Table Mountain fire

In March 2009 an intense fire burnt through most of the area infested by the *A. paradoxa* population on Table Mountain. This offered an opportunity to unravel other facets concerning the life history of *A. paradoxa*, such as its response to fire. In fire-prone ecosystems, tolerance to fire is a crucial attribute for the success of invading species. Fire is an essential ecosystem element not only because of its use as a management tool in preventing wildfires but also for its role in the management of endangered species, promotion of biodiversity, and water conservation.(van Wilgen et al., 1992) among others. Complete suppression of fire has been identified as a threat to about 4% of all endangered plant species in the USA (Kaye et al., 2001). This notwithstanding, fire is a major threat to some rare tropical plant species Kaye et al. (2001), especially if applied in inappropriate intensities, times and frequencies (Page, 2006). Writing particularly on invasive plant species, Harrod and Reichard (2001), state that except for a few cases, fire generally tends to promote persistence of invasives. Where fire has been avoided for long periods, invasive plant species seem to have failed to recruit and establish (Harrod and Reichard, 2001). For many plants, fire has been shown to enhance seed germination, and seedling establishment, and promote flowering and fruiting depending on the species (Schemske et al., 1994). In fire-prone areas, fires are also important for stimulating plant recruitment (Auld and Ooi, 2009). However, fire does kill some adult plants, and can result in recruitment failure in serotinous *Protea* species in fynbos where the intensity and frequency is too high (Bond et al., 1984). Many invasive species are well equipped for survival and proliferation in fire-prone ecosystems (Richardson and Cowling 1992). This attribute has led to its use in eradication programmes for alien plant invaders where seed bank depletion is the goal. Its use is reported to have been successfully used in reducing seed banks to as low as 1%. (Hastings and DiTomaso, 1996, and Holmes et al., 1987). Such a success could mean the populations were still small and eradication was implemented early (Rejmanek and Pitcairn, 2002).

It is against such a background that this research was conducted to investigate the soil seed bank dynamics especially after fire, and the role of mutualisms in early life of *A. paradoxa* and their implications on eradication and invasiveness. Such information is crucial for the current eradication efforts and for future reference in case of a novel invasion by the same species.

OBJECTIVES

The overall objectives were: 1) to determine how seed bank dynamics would affect the feasibility of eradicating *A. paradoxa*; and 2) to explore the role of mutualisms in the new environment during early life of *A. paradoxa*. The main research questions that were addressed are:

1. Assess seed bank dynamics of *A. paradoxa* by determining;
 - (a) The extent and distribution of seeds in the soil;
 - (b) The viability of *A. paradoxa* seed bank;
 - (c) The factors that trigger germination of *A. paradoxa* seeds;
 - (d) The longevity of the seed bank;
 - (e) The effect of the 2009 fire on seed bank depletion of *A. paradoxa* on Table Mountain;
 - (f) Details of post-fire recruitment from the seed bank and the impacting of this on the native flora.
2. The role of mutualisms in the early life of *A. paradoxa* was studied, with special reference to:
 - (a) Determining the identity of the bacterial symbionts that form mutualisms with *A. paradoxa* in South Africa;
 - (b) Examining the association between *A. paradoxa* and bacteria influence seedling growth and biomass accumulation and allocation; and,
 - (c) The effect of the above on growth.

Findings from this study will help in guiding managers on the direction the eradication efforts for *A. paradoxa* should take. Secondly they will add to our understanding of the role of mutualisms in the ecology of alien invaders, a role that would potentially help predict invasions as noted by Richardson et al (2000).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Species description

Acacia paradoxa, also called the kangaroo thorn, is native to Australia (Zenni et al., 2009), and earliest records of its presence in South Africa date back to 1937. It usually grows in woodlands or open forests. It is an erect spreading shrub that can attain a height of 4m. Its yellow flowers usually occur one per axil. Its seed pods are hairy and contain seeds with elaiosomes. It has short phyllodes and at the base of each there exist a pair of prickly stipules. Its thorny nature renders it non-palatable it has thus been saved where other *Acacia* have been eliminated due to grazing (Spooner and Lunt, 2004). It exhibits some polymorphism especially of the indumentum and its density. In South Africa, flowering occurs in spring (September to November) and seed production proceeds in the summer months of November to January (Zenni et al., 2009). While seed dispersal in Australia is by ants (Berg, 1975), in South Africa its dispersers have not been documented yet.

Location and description of study area

Table Mountain on the Cape Peninsula forms part of South Africa's Cape Floristic Region (CFR), a region of high biological diversity and endemism. *A. paradoxa* is however restricted to Devil's Peak on Table Mountain (33°57' 17.11" S; 18°26' 21.35"), and this is where the study was conducted. Geologically, Table Mountain forms part of a group derived from Palaeozoic quartzitic sandstones which produce sandy and acidic lithosol soil upon weathering (Boelhouwers, & Meiklejohn, 2002). The native vegetation of Table Mountain is mainly fynbos shrubland with the Proteaceae, Ericaceae, and Restionaceae being the dominant plant families (Anonymous, 2009)

Seed collection

Seeds used in this study were collected first by the WfW clearing team in 2008. Most of these were collected from seed pods on parent plants or the surface under them.. Later these seeds are broadly referred to as 'parent plants seeds' or 'seeds from seed pods.' Some seeds came from the seed bank analysis of un-burnt areas. More seeds were also collected from the soil seed bank after the fire from plots dug up after initial germination was observed. These seeds are referred to as 'soil seed bank seeds.'

Seed Bank analysis

Seed bank analysis was done first prior to germination, in May 2009. A second analysis was done after germination, after noticing profuse germination of the plant in areas that were not sampled in the May analysis. This discrepancy could be because most of the seed bank is confined to just below the canopy and the dry season plots just missed these areas.

Pre-germination seed bank assessment

A total of 20 samples were collected in areas which had dense and sparse distribution of *A. paradoxa* prior to its clearing in 2008. Soil samples were collected from a 0.25m² and 10 cm deep area with two batches 0-5 cm depth and 5-10 cm depth. The soils were put in labelled plastic bags and brought to the lab for analysis.

Post germination seed bank analysis

After the first rains, there was profuse germination of *A. paradoxa* and setting up plots for seed bank analysis was much easier. A total of 8 1m² plots were set up across the distribution range of *A. paradoxa*. In each of these plots, the total numbers of seedlings were counted and then the seedlings were weeded out. These plots were left for five months from July to October, 2009 to monitor any further emerging seedlings during this period. On 9 October 2009, each of the 8 plots was dug up (0-5 cm sample separate from 5-10cm sample) and the soil analyzed for seeds left after complete natural germination. The total number of seedlings recorded during the entire 5 months of monitoring, and the seeds still found in the soil constituted the soil seed bank.

Soil analysis for seeds

Soil seed bank analysis made use of two sieves, one on top of the other. One, of mesh size 3mm (containing soil sample), was placed on top of one with mesh size 1mm which was then placed on a closed “soil trap.” The equipment is shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. Soil sieving equipment, comprising two sieves, one on top of the other, placed on a vibrating machine with modifiable amplitude that sieved the soil.

Seeds of *A. paradoxa* were collected both in the 3 mm sieve and 1 mm sieve. No seeds escaped the 1 mm sieve and all soil was collected in the ‘trap.’ Seed identification was made easy by the characteristic shape and colour of the seeds. To determine accuracy, a known number of seeds was placed in soils and sieved it and the number of seeds missed was counted. This exercise proved helpful at improving detection and identification of seeds within a soil matrix. Its accuracy was 99% on average.

Test of germination triggers of Acacia paradoxa.

The germinability of the seeds was assessed alongside factors affecting germination that were to be investigated namely, differential heat, and smoke.

Differential heating and germination in A. paradoxa

A total of 300 seeds in replicates of 25 were used. 100 seeds were heated in an autoclave for 10 minutes at 100 °C, another 100 seeds were heated for 10 minutes at 60 °C and another 100 were left unheated as a control. Two whatman No. 1 filter papers were placed at the bottom of a 9 cm petri dish and moistened with distilled water. 25 seeds were then placed in the dishes after being washed in 70% alcohol and later with distilled water to remove any microbes. This formed a total of 4 replicates for each of the treatments. The seeds were then covered by another filter paper and white tissue paper. The tissue paper was used to help conserve moisture as the experiment was being done in the green house and moisture loss was high. The petri dishes were then covered by a black plastic sheet. Greenhouse day time temperatures ranged between 7°C and 21°C. The petri dishes were watered every two to four days depending on the observed moisture levels. Observations were made daily from one week after setting up the experiment, for 48 days. Seeds with emerged radical of length of 5-10 mm were deemed to have germinated.

Impact of smoke on germination

A total of 100 seeds were treated with smoke water. 2ml of stock solution was diluted to make up a 1:250 v/v solution. The seeds were then soaked in the solution for 24 hours and germinated on filter paper in petri-dishes. Another 100 seeds were soaked in water as a control. 25 seeds were germinated in 4 petri dishes, making four replicates for experiment and control.

The Tetrazolium test for seed viability

The tetrazolium test is a quick method used to determine seed viability. This test is based on the principle that the colourless compound Triphenyl tetrazolium chloride is reduced to formazan, a red and stable non-diffusible compound in all living cells; hence red colouration of a seed is a definite indicator of its viability (Lakon, 1949).

The method is generally considered the most accurate for determining seed viability (Sawma and Mohler, 2002) and it is officially recognized by the International Seed Testing Association (Vujanovic et al., 2000).

Solution preparation

The solution was prepared by dissolving 1g of 2, 3, 5,-triphenyl tetrazolium chloride (TZ) in 100ml of distilled water, making a 1% solution. The pH was detected to be 6.7 and this was within the acceptable range that allow for optimal staining.

Seed treatment protocol

A total of 200 seeds were tested for viability, 100 from the soil seed bank and 100 collected from the parent plants in January of 2008. The seeds were divided into 4 replicates of 50 seeds each. Seeds were pricked for the reason of allowing water imbibitions. This treatment allowed easy peeling off of the seed coat. Water imbibition does not only initiate and activate the whole germination process but also ensures fast and complete absorption of the salt. These seeds were put in Petri dishes completely immersed in the tetrazolium salt solution and left for 48 hours at room temperature. After 48 hours, the seeds were removed and rinsed with distilled water 4 times to remove any excess salts. They were then examined under the dissecting microscope.

Assessment of impacts of recruitment from seed bank on other species

To determine the impacts of seedling recruitment of *A. paradoxa* on other species, a total of 57 plots each 1m² were sampled. In each plot, the total number of *A. paradoxa* was determined (given as density in number/m²). The number of other species was determined and expressed as density per m². Morphospecies were used because identification to species level of the seedlings was not possible. Other species were categorized as grasses, trees, herbs and shrubs (see attached data sheet in appendix). The relative coverage was determined for *A. Paradoxa* and other categories of species. This was done by dividing each plot into 4 parts, each representing, 25% coverage. This plot division was used to estimate the relative coverage.

Figure 2. Transects sampled across the distribution (as of 2008.) of the *A. paradoxa* around Devil's Peak (Table Mountain National Park). On the map above, transect appear dark green on which are green plots. 1 m² plots were set out 10m apart. (Map courtesy of John Wilson, at Centre for Invasion biology, Stellenbosch University)

Role of mutualisms in early life

Bacterial Isolation and culturing

Root nodules of *A. paradoxa* on Table Mountain were collected to isolate nitrogen-fixing bacteria cultures. The root nodules were first washed under tap water to remove soil. Root nodules were then transferred into sterile water and left overnight to absorb water at 4⁰C. After water absorption they were sterilised by immersing them in 70% ethanol and then into 3.5% sodium hypochlorite for 5 minutes. Following sterilization, root nodules were washed 5 times in distilled water. Each root nodule from a specific plant was then crushed in a microfuge tube containing 3% v/v of 30% glycerol. 30 L of this suspension were serially diluted from x⁰ to x⁻⁶ where x is the original concentration of the suspension.

Each of the suspension was streaked on Yeast-extract Manito Agar (YMA), containing 0.04g yeast, 0.5g K₂HPO₄, 0.2g MgSO₄, 0.1g NaCl, 15g Bacteriological agar, 10g manitol, and 1% (v/v) of 0.25% (m/v) Congo Red, pH 6.6. The streaked plates were incubated at 28 °C for 3-8 days with observations for bacteriological growth made every two days. Colonies from the initial plates were re-streaked to obtain pure cultures. After re-streaking, a portion of the culture from each isolate was Gram stained to confirm purity of cultures and Gram status of the bacteria. The six isolates are coded PAR 1 to PAR 6, representing the six plants from which the nodules were collected.

PCR amplification and DNA sequencing

The complete 16S to 23S intergenic spacer (IGS) region was targeted for amplified. IGS region is informative to below the species level and often utilised in bacterial systematics (Laguerre et al., 1996). The primers used were FGPS1490-72 (5'-TGCGGCTGGATCCCCTCCTT-3') and FGPL132-38 (5'-CCGGGTTTCCCCATTCGG-3') after (Normand et al., 1996 and Ponsonet and Nesme, 1994) and the 800-1000 were used.

DNA purification and gel running

Amplified PCR products were purified using QIAquick. The PCR amplification conditions were 96 °C for 2 minutes, 30 cycles for 30 seconds at 96 °C, 30 seconds at 56 °C, 30 seconds at 72 °C, followed by 5 minutes at 72 °C. The gel was run in 2% agarose gel for 40 minutes at 110v.

Green house experiment; growth and rhizobial inoculation

Plants were grown from seeds of *A. paradoxa* germinated in Petri-dishes on filter paper. The seeds were initially scarified by heating them at 120 °C for 10 minutes to stimulate germination, and then washed in 70% alcohol to sterilize them. Germination started after 7 days and all seeds with radical length of between 1-3 cm were transferred into growing pots with soil for further growth.

Figure 3. Germinated seeds that were planted

Seeds were not germinated straight into growing pots to avoid failed germination from bringing in gaps in replicate numbers, so only germinated seeds were transferred to growing pots.

A total of 30 seeds were planted, 20 in soils sterilised at 120 °C for 30 minutes, and 10 in unsterilized soil. All the soil used was from Table Mountain where seeds and nodules were collected from. Inoculation was done by using bacterial suspensions in distilled water. The suspension was prepared by taking a colony of fast growing *rhizobia* and putting it in Yeast Manitol Broth (YMB). These *rhizobia* in broth were incubated for 72 hours at 28 °C to allow bacterial population growth. A 1:50v/v suspension was made using the cultured bacteria in YMB and sterile water and used to inoculate each of the ten plants grown in sterilized soil. A control was one with plants growing in ‘natural’ unsterilized soil.

Biomass analysis

Plants were harvested 10 weeks after planting. The soil round the plant was carefully removed to expose the entire root system of the plants. The plant height and number of nodules were determined. The plants were then cut, separating the shoot and root systems. The fresh weights were then measured using electronic balance. These samples were then placed in paper envelopes and dried for 24 hours in the oven at 50⁰C. Dry masses of shoots and roots were measured and recorded.

The total biomass was calculated as the sum of root and shoot biomass. The shoot to root ratio was calculated by dividing shoot biomass with root biomass.

Ethical Considerations

As the work involved an invasive alien plant species that is currently confined to a small area of the Western Cape Province, I used the following procedure to ensure that the species was not accidentally spread to new areas in the course of the study. Soil samples used in seed bank determination in the laboratory were autoclaved and heated to kill any surviving seeds before being disposed back on Table Mountain. Boots and equipment used in the field were cleaned of any soils before leaving Devil's Peak. This ensured that no seeds are allowed to be further dispersed beyond by the research team. In the green house and growth rooms, there was close monitoring to ensure that no plantlet is allowed out. After all the growth analysis was completed, the plants were dried and burned.

RESULTS

Results on seed bank determination were assessed using a combination soil analysis and germination monitoring. This was done because in an initial soil analysis, conducted before the rains in May, 2009, only 2 seeds were found soil in 19 of 20 randomly chosen sites. Soon after the rains, in late June, profuse seedlings germination was noticed and a second seed bank analysis, combining field germination and a further soil analysis, was deemed vital.

Figure 4. Vertical distribution of *A. paradoxa* seeds in the soil.

The results show that 90% of seeds occur in the top 10cm of the soil profile. More than 55% of the seeds were found in the top 5cm of soil (Fig. 3). These data were collected from sites that had been disturbed, so there is a chance that the vertical distribution of the seed bank was disturbed. The sampling site had deep loose soil and had a dense patch of *A. paradoxa* before clearing in 2008. These results are in agreement with Richardson and Kluge (2008) who reported 3cm soil depth as where most Acacia seeds are and that some can be found as deep as 8cm.

Triggers of germination

Figure 5. Effects of different germination cues on *A. paradoxa* seeds

Heating to a temperatures of 100 °C was the most effective in stimulating germination, followed by smoke and heating to 60 °C (Fig. 4). The seeds used were from soil seed bank collected last in 2008 and from parent plants. These results indicate that moderately high temperatures stimulate germination more than do lower temperatures. Natural germination in this species is even lower. In a field scenario where fire occurs, it can be implied that there should also be differential germination stimulation reflecting variation in fire intensities. These results revealed that germinability of *A. paradoxa* is high but only with stimulation. Whether seedling recruitment after a fire in community with a known soil seed bank could help map out fire intensity would be an interesting idea to investigate.

Figure. 6. Germination was staggered over the 6-week germination period, with a peak after 3 weeks for all treatments. The experiment was set up on July 16 and terminated on September 2, 2009.

A similar spread of germination over several weeks was also observed in the field (Fig. 7). In the field though it was observed that while at some sites seedlings had emerged by late June, at this time some sites had no seedlings. By early July, other sites had seedlings coming up as well. This differential germination in the field could be due to the patchy spatial distribution of fire intensities that would have stimulated germination to different extents. At sites where early germination was observed, there had been some of the densest patches of *A. paradoxa* in 2008 that had been cut. These may have provided the fuel for hot fires. It could also be due to the soil properties because where there was early detection of seedling emergence, the soil was sandy, loose and well drained while where there was delayed germination the soil was loamy and compact. Overall, this germination pattern suggests an adaptation to growth in areas with erratic optimal growth conditions.

Burnt area.

Un-burnt area

Month of Sampling

Month of Sampling

Figure 7. Comparative seed bank depletion for burnt and un-burnt areas over time, after an initial weeding of some plots.

Depletion progressed more in burnt areas than in un-burnt areas (Fig. 7). The reason that more seedlings kept coming up in burnt areas than in un-burnt areas could be because of

differential heating of the soil profile that could have stimulated germination to different levels but this could not be verified. Overall seedling recruitment was 236 seedlings /m², ranging from 64 seedlings / m² to 660 m². There was a difference in overall seedling recruitment between un-burnt areas and burnt areas. Areas that burnt had an average of 315 m² while those that did not burn had an average of 76 seedlings /m².

Figure 8. Overall spread of germination in *A. paradoxa*.

The number of upcoming seedlings with time was not statistically significant ($p = 0.317$) for burnt areas than un-burnt areas. A close look however show that more seeds kept coming up with time in burnt than in un-burnt sites (Fig. 8).

Table 2. Number of rotten seed and the viability test results for the un-germinated seeds.

Treatment	Number of rotten seeds.	Number of intact seeds.	Viability test sample	% viable seeds
100 °C	3	30	30	93
60 °C	2	61	30	91
Smoke	0	56	30	97
Control	2	96	30	95
TZ test control.	-	-	30	97

It was found that failure to germinate was not due to loss of viability. After the experiment un-germinated seeds showed a high viability (Table 2). This was irrespective of the seed source i.e. whether straight from plants or from the seed bank. The tetrazolium tests for viability were conducted on both seed bank and those collected straight from parent plants. This was to find out whether time in the soil impacts on viability. In 100 seed viability test conducted on seeds bank seeds collected in August this year, the viability was found to be 96% with 4% seeds dead. This result is the same as was found when a similar test was done on seeds collected while still in seeds pods. This signifies that time in the soil seed bank (at least for the relatively short period that was investigated) has no impact on viability.

Figure 10. Tetrazolium (TZ) test results for *A. paradoxa* seeds. A shows positive test for viability, B shows non-viable seeds and C is the control. (Photo courtesy: CJ Scheepers, Centre for Invasion Biology, Stellenbosch University).

The viability and test results correlate strongly with germinability at 100°C heating. There is no correlation between viability and natural germinability. This later discrepancy can be attributed to the high seed coat imposed dormancy of the seeds that is broken after

scarification by heat. During the germinability test, it was observed that water entry was the main limiting factor to germination. Heat seems to affect the seeds in such a way as to create or enhance a water entry point.

This assertion stems from the observation that seeds with an elaiosome intact did not germinate even after scarification at 100⁰C while the same scarification temperature triggered 98% germination in seeds without the elaiosome from seed bank. This observation presupposes that the elaiosome might have been blocking water entry. When these seeds were pricked with a sharp needle, they acquired water faster and germination was observed after 7 days. Unsatisfied with why seeds with elaiosomes couldn't germinate after 100⁰C treatment, these seeds were further compared to those from the seed bank in a further experiment (Fig. 10).

Figure 11. Box-and-whisker plots summarizing water relations of soil seed bank seeds and ‘non-soil’ seeds.

In plot A seeds collected from pods (before they join the soil seed bank) had higher masses than those from soil seed bank although the difference was not significant, ($p = 0.610$). In plot B, both seed types did not absorb water for 36 days during the germination test. After this period they were weighed. There was no significant difference ($p = 0.087$) between the two seed sets. To allow for water entry they were pricked with a needle. 24 hours after this treatment they were all swollen due to water acquisition. When weighed, seeds from the seed bank had significantly lower mass ($p = 0.0001$) compared to those gotten from parent plants, plot C. When calculated, the amount of water each seed category had absorbed, there was a significant difference ($p = 0.0028$) between seeds from the soil seed bank and those collected before they joined the soil seed bank. These seeds were then germinated no variation in germinability was detected (Fig. 11).

Seed bank depletion due to fire.

Table 1. The extent of depletion of the seed bank, after the fire.

Site No.	Seedling recruitment.	Remnant seed bank	Total seed bank	% seed bank depleted due to germination.	Viability of remnant seed bank
X(SB)	663	228	891	74.4%	98%
1	313	202	515	60.8%	96%
2	617	343	960	64.3%	96%
3	124	3567	3691	3.4%	99%
4	80	552	632	12.7%	91%
5	96	1	97	99.0%	-
6	275	0	275	100%	-
7	77	8	85	90.6%	0%
8	65	4	69	94.2%	0%

There was a significantly greater depletion of seed bank in burnt sites than un-burnt sites. Plot X(SB) had its seedling density determined, seedlings weeded and soils were collected to assess remnant seed bank without waiting for a further 3 months for complete germination.

Plot 8 was at a site where there had been a fire three years back (around 2005) and so had been further cleared by Working for Water team in 2008. Sites 3, 4, and 8, were un-burnt during the 2009 fire and they served as controls. It was difficult to have equal number of plots as almost the entire distribution range of *A. paradoxa* had burnt. For un-burnt areas (site 8), the small seed bank has almost been completely depleted. But this site is where there had been a fire a few years back before the 2009 one. Whether this year's (2009) germination had depleted the seed bank at this site can only be implied as a seed bank analysis of 14 (0.25m²) plots at the site contained only two unviable seeds, representing a seeds bank of less than 1seed/m² (Table 1). Sites 5, 6, and 7 had similar soil properties. Seed bank depletion is high relative to other burnt areas (Table 1). This could be attributed to the soil type and profile which was hard and compact. The seeds could have remained on top relatively and that whatever was available either germinated due to stimulation and the rest were killed by fire. All seeds collected in site 5 and 7 were burnt and non-viable.

The post germination seed bank analysis, revealed that the seed bank size of *A. paradoxa* is bigger (3,567 m⁻²), than 1000 m⁻² as reported in Zenni et al (2009). Such a discrepancy could be attributed to the method of analysis used. In this study, a whole 1m² plot was dug up 10cm deep and this improved the accuracy.

Impacts of A. paradoxa post-fire recruitment on native flora

B

Figure 9. The impacts of *A. paradoxa* density and % coverage on the density, overall species richness and of herbs and shrubs

Density of *A. paradoxa* showed a significant impacts richness of shrubs and herbs ($p = 0.036$), and overall species richness ($p = 0.030$). *A. paradoxa* % cover showed moderate negative correlations with the species overall (Fig. 9). Since in some site, *A. paradoxa* was the sole tree germinating after rains, its density should have acted to reduce the number of other native flora that germinated much later.

Role of mutualisms

Identification of bacterial isolates

Isolated PAR 3, PAR 4, and PAR 6 were deemed pure enough to be sent for sequencing. The DNA from other isolates has been kept at -20°C . The bacterial colonies for isolates from PAR 1, PAR 2, and PAR 5 will be re-streaked to obtain pure cultures for a fresh PCR and sequencing, while PCR will be redone on PAR 3, and modifying annealing temperatures to try and obtain a better sequence.

Figure 12. PCR product of rDNA IGS region of 6 rhizobial isolates from *A. paradoxa* (abbreviated PAR 1-6) and the marker on the far right.

Isolates 3, 4, and 6 had their DNA purified for sequencing. Sequence for PAR 3 was not further analysed because it had a lot of background noise in its sequence. The sequences obtained for PAR 6 and PAR 4 were aligned and blasted on GenBank and they closely resemble *Rhizobium leguminosarum viciae* and *Bradyrhizobium* sp. GenBank accession numbers are AY491952 and DQ311115 respectively. The species *Rhizobium leguminosarum* and genus *Bradyrhizobium*, are present in the native range of *A. paradoxa* in Australia (Thral et al, 2005).

Mutualisms and dry mass accumulation

Table 3. Correlation coefficients between the number of nodules of roots and dry masses of shoot, roots, whole plant biomass, and shoot/root ratio.

Number of nodules in treatment	Shoot Dry mass	Root dry mass	Total biomass	Shoot to root ratio
Rh+	0.671 0.034**	0.433 0.211	0.638 0.047**	-0.317 0.372
Rh-	0.564 0.089	0.248 0.489	0.528 0.117	0.135 0.710
NS	0.411 0.238	0.667 0.008**	0.458 0.183	-0.547 0.102

Treatments: Rh+ (rhizobium inoculated), Rh- (no rhizobia and soil sterilised), NS (Natural soil i.e. soil straight from Table Mountain and no inoculation with bacteria). *P*-values in italics and ** means correlation is significant at $P < 0.05$.

Worth noting here is that in plants growing in sterilised and un-inoculated soils there is no correlation what so ever irrespective of some two plants nodulating. The significant correlation between number of nodules and root dry mass for plants growing in natural soils could mean naturally *A. paradoxa* invests more in below ground biomass but where nitrogen is not limiting due to abundant fixing symbionts as is the case for treatment Rh+, then biomass allocation is more towards above ground biomass (Table 3). The differential allocation of resources to shoots or root is very plastic (Wilson, 1988), and so the incremental nutrients richness in inoculated plants could as well be the reason why they have more shoot biomass compared to the control.

Table 4. Variation between different treatments of five parameters as affected by ANOVAs done in SAS

Treatment	Height	No. nodules	Root DW	Plant DW	Shoot DW	Shoot DW/ root DW ratio
NP	66.5b*	3.3b	0.007b	0.050b	0.043b	6.86ab
RH-	65.8b	0.6c	0.005b	0.039b	0.034b	10.35a
RH+	108.6a	6.6a	0.018a	0.099a	0.081a	5.50b
<i>P</i> -value	<i>0.0002</i>	<i>0.0001</i>	<i>0.0008</i>	<i>0.0003</i>	<i>0.0012</i>	<i>0.0929</i>

There is significant variation among plants treated differently. Plants with rhizobia inoculation show a high variability for all the tested parameters compared to the control and that where soils were sterilised. *Means with the same letter are not significantly different at 5% level (LSD).

What is more interesting is the overall correlations between number of nodules and the other attributes measured. There are insignificant differences between plants grown in natural soils and those without rhizobial inoculation except for number of nodules and the shoot to root ratio (Table4). This shows that there is a critical number of nodules required for there to be significant biomass accumulation. The graphs below give a summary.

Figure 13. Graphs showing the correlations between number of nodule and plant biomass (A), height (B), root biomass(C), shoot biomass (D), and shoot to root ratio (E).

There are strong positive correlations between the number of nodules and plant height, plant biomass, shoot dry mass, and root dry mass. This makes sense as the number of nodules has a bearing on the amount of nitrogen a plant fixes hence the amount of growth dry mass accumulated. There is a strong negative correlation ($p = 0.0195$, $r = -0.425$, conf. Int. 0.95), though between number of nodules and shoot to root dry mass ratio. But an ANOVA test for variability finds insignificant variation of this ratio across the three treatments, refer to table 4. This correlation though significant could be attributed to the contribution from plants growing in sterilised soil (Rh-) which had high ratios of shoot to root but with negligible nodulation. This ratio could also mean that, overall number of nodules promoted more of root biomass accumulation than shoot. It's an observation that warrants further investigation though.

DISCUSSION

The seed bank of *A. paradoxa* on Table Mountain is as variable as the topography. The nature and composition of the soil seem to have an effect on how deep the seeds occur in the soil. The highest seed density recorded was 3,567 seeds /m². This density is similar compared to all the other Australian Acacias in South Africa for which Richardson and Kluge (2008) reported a range of between 2,000 and 48,000 seeds/ m², but is higher than what was reported by Zenni et al, (2009) of 1000 seeds/ m². The vertical distribution of seeds was for *A. paradoxa* reported here was found at a site with loose and deep soil with minimal rocks. The topographic variability on Table Mountain entails variability in seed distribution but as Pareja et al. (1985) observes, such a variable topography further affects, seed germinability and seedling establishment because it creates micro-sites with diverse prescriptions of growth-impacting environmental regimes. Seed density decreased with depth, but some substantial seeds, 13%, were found in depths 10-15 cm on a disturbed site. This underscored how disturbance can affect distribution of seeds in the soil and provide a challenge for their depletion. Seeds that are deeply buried in the soil, such as these, are obstructed from germination triggers (Holmes, 2002), and can therefore remain in the soil for much longer. However where the seeds are small, as is the case with *A. paradoxa*, they tend to lack resources to successfully germinate from such depths and establish viable seedlings (Bond, 1999).

Above all, deeply buried seeds usually tend to be older as a result, when they germinate, there tends to be slow germination and growth rates, seedlings have abnormalities, plants die before maturity, sterile plants are common and polyploidy could all be the result (Crocker, 1938). In this study, differences in water acquisition observed on soil seed bank seeds and those from seed pods (Fig. 10) could be due to seed deterioration that accompanies ageing, with time in the soil. It is known that as ageing proceeds, there is a decrease in numbers of viable cells (Walters et al., 2005) a scenario that should affect water uptake. In this study though, seeds from the seed bank have as high viability and germinability as those collected straight from parent pods. If the discrepancy in water imbibition is attributable to ageing, then further effects could be observed on seedling survival, a situation not studied here. Woodstock and Tao (1981) though, did observe reduced survival in seedlings from aged seeds. This shows that a really old seed bank could be less worrisome for conservation purposes. In this study, 42 % seedlings germinated from seed bank seeds, died before 2 weeks. While this observation may not be linked to seed age but green house and soil conditions, it makes such a determination worthwhile.

Such observations as Crocker's should not be seen as downplaying risk associated with the high seed bank viability for *A. paradoxa* as found in this study. Some invasive species such as legumes, a group constituting *A. paradoxa*, owe their invasive status to the possession of viable seeds in their dense seed bank (Holmes et al., 1987). The eradication of such species requires that their seed bank, a source of propagules for recruitment, is depleted (Myers et al., 1998). Due to low natural germinability and high dormancy attributed to hard seed coats in plants such as *A. paradoxa*, it becomes a challenge to deplete the seed bank using routine clearing operations as an eradication technique since clearing alone does little to eliminate the seed bank. But even when germination is stimulated by triggers such as fire, the resultant recruitment at the onset of the rainy season is mainly by such invaders. Successful germination as observed after the fires provides a leap in the invasive potential of an alien plants (Greenberg et al, 2001) and Pauchard et al. (2007), considers such fast colonization and invasion of burned areas by invasive plants as one of their major adaptations. This was observed on Table Mountain, where after the 2009 fire, *A. paradoxa* was the sole tree species recruiting; Fig, 11, shows site with *A. Paradoxa* seedlings only, two months into the rainy season.

Figure 14: In this photo, taken from a heavily burnt site, the only plant species to be seen is *Acacia paradoxa*. Photo taken on 28 July 2009

In some sites, the density of *A. Paradoxa* seedlings reached as high as 663 /m² and for most plots set up in July, *A. paradoxa* comprised close to 100% of the plants. Even when other species of grasses shrubs and herbs emerged, *A. paradoxa* remained a dominant species in most previously infested sites where it had been cleared in 2008. As at now, October, 2009, the coverage and density of other native species has increased, it remains to be investigated how *A. paradoxa* will interact with these annuals.

Figure 15: Competition facing *A. paradoxa*, mainly from a native *Ageratum* species.

It has to be reported that of the 57 plots sampled during assessment of impacts of *A. paradoxa* on native flora, only one plot was found to contain a tree species. The dominant native species were of grasses, herbs and shrubs with geophytism a well represented growth form. This could prove advantageous since when the other species die back in summer, surviving *A. paradoxa* will have reduced competition this could promote its survival. While herbivory in *A. paradoxa* has not been documented for South Africa, it was observed on 24 July, 2009 on some seedlings. On a sample of 170 seedlings, 5% had their tips eaten off. It could not be determined what animal was responsible but an insect was seen on one such plant. The factors that affect the survival of *A. paradoxa* remain to be fully determined.

Seed bank longevity and eradication.

This study has shown that seed bank viability in *A. paradoxa* (Tables 1 and 2) is high and that the germinability is equally high (Fig . 5). The seed bank therefore is a real concern for any eradication efforts under way. When eradication of an alien invasive species has been

chosen as an option, it becomes vital to have an idea as to how long it will take to eradicate the target species. The issues of seed bank size, its viability, germinability, recruitment and survival are all vital components for consideration in eradication efforts for invasive plants. As discussed above, eradication of any species is not complete until viable propagules in the soil are depleted. The amount of propagules in the soil at any time during an eradication effort is affected by natural losses due to germination and death, but also replenishment from any surviving plants (Zamora et al., 1989). Where mature trees can be eradicated through conventional clearing, the remnant question is how long can viable seed bank last in the soil during eradication? While determination of seed longevity requires long periods of study, (Cohen, 1966) model as modified in Zamora et al. (1989) predicts the amount of time required to eradicate the viable seed bank. The model as modified is

$$S_{t+1} = S_t - S_t G - D(S_t - S_t G) + GY_t S_t P_y E_y \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Where S_t is the current seed bank, G is the germinable component of the seed bank, D is dead portion of the seed bank, Y_t number of seed produced per germinated seedling whose probability of successful reproduction is P_y , and E_y is the probability of it escaping control i.e. chance that a plant is missed during eradication efforts. Solving the above model equation further yields a number of applicable equations that would be applied to reveal the dynamics of *A. paradoxa*.

$$S_{t+1} = [(1 - G)(1 - D) + GY_t P_y E_y] S_t \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

$$= [(1 - G)(1 - D) + GY_t P_y E_y] [(1 - G)(1 - D) + GY_{t-1} P_y E_y] S_{t-1}$$

$$= [(1 - G)(1 - D) + GY_t P_y E_y] [(1 - G)(1 - D) + GY_{t-1} P_y E_y] \dots [(1 - G)(1 - D) + GY_0 P_y E_y] S_0$$

This simplifies to,

$$S_{t+1} = [(1 - G)(1 - D) + GY_0 P_y E_y]^{t+1} S_0 \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

Equation (3) can be used to calculate how much seed will still be in the soil at a known time (t+1). If the desire is to know how long will it take to reduce seed bank to almost zero then equation (3) can be further simplified by taking natural logs of both sides yields.

$$\ln\left(\frac{S_{t+1}}{S_t}\right) = \ln\{[(1 - G)(1 - D) + GY_t P_y E_y]^{t+1}\} \dots\dots\dots (4)$$

This further simplifies to give

$$(t + 1) \ln[(1 - G)(1 - D) + GY_t P_y E_y] = \ln\left(\frac{S_{t+1}}{S_t}\right) \text{ And}$$

$$t + 1 = \ln\left(\frac{S_{t+1}}{S_t}\right) \div \ln[(1 - G)(1 - D) + GY_t P_y E_y] \dots\dots\dots (5)$$

Where (t+1) is a future time that can be determined given all the parameters of the model. Let such future time be *t* and the model equation becomes;

$$t = \ln\left(\frac{S_{t+1}}{S_t}\right) \div \ln[(1 - G)(1 - D) + GY_t P_y E_y] - 1.$$

When applied to *A. paradoxa* using data partly obtained in this project, where the seed bank is 1500 seeds /m², 7% natural germination, 98% germination at high temperature (100⁰C), 64% germination at moderate heat (60⁰C), 7% natural germination, and 3% decayed seeds (i.e. 97% viability), the model simulates a number of scenarios that in turn provide a number of options that the eradication effort can apply. The table below gives a hypothetical scenario for different management options using data mostly obtained in this study.

Table 5. How different eradication techniques would deplete the seed bank in *A. paradoxa*. The values here have been derived from the model assuming that 50% of the germinated seedlings survive to reproductive age and that each surviving plant produces just 10 seeds.

Management Option		Time taken to achieve desired eradication (extent of seed bank depletion)	
		1seed/m ² remaining (Years from present)	0.02 seeds/m ² (Years from present)
Germination stimulation	Natural (7%)	54	66
	65%	7	8
	98%	2	2
Efficiency of eradication (varying <i>E_y</i>)	99.9%	54	66
	90%	56	68
	80%	58	70
Combined approach (germination enhancement and efficiency of eradication)	65%,99.9%	7	8
	98%,99.9%	2	2
	65%,95%	7	8
	98%95%	2	3

NB: Under germination stimulation, 65% represents a moderate fire that stimulates 65% germination and 98% represent a hot fire that stimulates 98% of seeds to germinate. On efficiency of eradication, the percentages reflect the extent to which the efforts go to eliminate the species e.g. at 99.9%, 90% and 80%, eradication, the probability of escaping control (*E_y*) is 0.001, 0.1, and 0.2 respectively.

From this hypothetical set up, the model points to germination stimulation as a key to depletion of the seed bank. Whether moderate fires or hot fires are used to stimulate germination, their impacts are noticeable in the short term.

If germination is not stimulated, it would take more than 50 years to reduce the seed bank to 1 seed/m² and more than 65 years to reduce it to zero. With germination stimulation by fire, it takes between 2- 8 years to deplete the seed bank. Another point to note is the effectiveness of eradication. Where plants are missed during eradication, as was noted by Zenni et al. (2009), this does increase the time it will take to eradicate the species. The model shows that a combined high germination stimulation and effective eradication translates into the shortest time in eradicating the species. The main model limitation here though is the high variability in seed bank sizes at different locations on the mountain due to topographic heterogeneity. A clear understanding would be gotten through further observation to determine actual values of P_y and Y_t for *A. paradoxa* which were assumed in the above analysis. This notwithstanding, the scenarios, as predicted by the model still stand and could be applied for management purposes.

Role of Mutualisms in early life of A. paradoxa

These results show how *Acacia paradoxa* responds to symbiosis with nitrogen fixing bacteria, and that the bacterial symbionts are effective as evidenced in the influence of nodule number on plant biomass. It is known for example that fast growth, as could be attained due to such a mutualistic relationship would lead to quick canopy closure and reduction of competitor biomass (Dumroese et al., 2009). The role of nitrogen-fixing bacteria on plant life affects not only growth but also establishment and survival, attributes that are critical to successful invasion of plants. A study by Thrall et al. (2000) found that establishment of inoculated *A. paradoxa* increased 2 fold compared to un-inoculated plants. Thrall et al. also found significantly high short term and long term survival in inoculated *A. paradoxa* than in un-inoculated plants. Establishment and survival though is affected by a number of factors apart from association with a mutualist and these include moisture stress and herbivory (Thrall et al. (2005). Of particular importance to note is the role of nitrogen fixing bacteria to a plant during times of water stress.

For *Acacias*, Thrall et al. (2000) observes that, where moisture is not limiting their root systems grow aggressively and effectively ‘hunt’ for nitrogen where as under water stress the resulting poor root development mean dependence on atmospheric nitrogen, and mutualistic nitrogen fixation become very crucial to their survival. The lack of significant variation between plants growing in sterilized soil and those growing in inoculated soils is also supported by Thrall et al’s work. The extent to which inoculation would significantly affect parameters depends on the amount of *rhizobia* already in the soil. Since root infection and nodulation depends on the establishment of a threshold population of *rhizobia* (Purchase and Nutman, 1957 in Thrall et al., 2005), these results suggest that on Table Mountain there exist such a threshold population of these bacteria as evidenced in infection and nodulation of *A. paradoxa* in untreated soils from the site. This means *A. paradoxa* growth stands to benefit from forming such mutualisms as the presence of rhizobia is not a limiting factor. Further, *Bradyrhizobium spp.* and *Rhizobium leguminosarum* as isolated from *A. paradoxa* of Table Mountain have been also identified by Thrall et al. (2005) as native bacteria species that nodulates this plant in its native range. *A. paradoxa* therefore has an advantage as it’s not obliged to forge new mutualisms with native micro-biota in order to benefit from mutualistic associations. It should be mentioned though that plants have been found to nodulate in novel habitat without inoculation by their native symbionts; a phenomenon Richardson et al. (2000) attributes to either wide distribution of effective *rhizobia* or lack of selectivity in invaders for rhizobial symbionts. It would be interesting to investigate whether these bacterial symbionts are here due to co-introduction or they have been acquired from native legumes. If the later is the case, then the ‘source’ indigenous legumes could be vital in predicting potential distribution patterns of *Acacias*. Like in other studies, the impacts of rhizobial interactions investigated here provide some evidence for a situation where effective nodulation confers on a plant an added advantage in ecosystems where competition, drought, and low nutrient levels are major stresses. This study though did not investigate the role of such mutualism on the competitive ability of *A. paradoxa* in its range on Table Mountain. This, along with the fact that the experiment was done in the green house, limits the extent of extrapolation of these results to the natural environment scenario. The results however are a pointer to a potential role in its being a better competitor. But this assertion needs to be further investigated.

RECOMMENDATIONS

As seen from the model, the seed bank is a major threat to eradication efforts as it replenished propagules overtime. In the case of the study species here, there is potential of eliminating seed rain completely by removing the germinated plants before they flower and produce seeds. The remaining challenge would be to deal with the ‘population’ still in the soil as viable seed bank. This should take several years but the following recommendations should help in the overall eradication plan: First, repeated monitoring of the area should be routine to detect any emerging plants. This should be easy for *A. paradoxa* considering that the known population patch size is small. This monitoring should be linked to detection of other aliens that could potentially fill the empty niche created due to *A. paradoxa* removal, as it occurred when *Sesbania punicea* was controlled only to be replaced by *Lantana camara* in South Africa (Mack and Lonsdale, 2002). This approach is important as the implicit goal of alien plant removal is the resurgence of native flora (Van et al., 1998); hence replacement of one invasive by another is retrogressive from a conservation perspective. The use of fire to stimulate germination could be an option in trying to eradicate the species by depleting the seed bank. Hastings and DiTomaso (1996) reported complete elimination of seed production and a 99% reduction in seed bank of the invasive plant, *Centaurea solstitialis* after three years of consecutive prescribed burning. In the case of its use within fynbos, fire does promote recruitment of fire adapted species (Holmes and Cowling, 1997) but also it has been found to promote invasion of this ecosystem by alien such as *Acacia* spp. (Richardson et al., 1987). This notwithstanding, Holmes et al. (1987) reports of a successful use of fire in managing *Acacia saligna* where 1 year prescribed burning burn decreased seed bank by 90%. Plant recruitment monitoring and clearing after a fire is crucial. In the case of *A. saligna* control, where follow up was not done, a depleted seed bank of 7 seeds /m² was restored to 740 seeds /m². The use of fire as a management option has to be treated with caution considering other undesirable effects such as promoting ecosystem invisibility and long term changes in ecosystem composition (Pauchard, et al., 2007). Mack and Lonsdale (2002) include killing of native species due to excesses of prescribed fires beyond natural fire regimes, and miss-timing with critical phenological phases for native flora. Furthermore, such fire opens up niches for occupancy not only for natives but yet new invaders. Finally there is need to incorporate deliberate measures meant to reduce post eradication susceptibility to re-

invasion (Zavaleta et al., 2001), this could be done by assessing habitat integrity and understand how it has changed with the invasion and whether restorative steps would promote recruitment of native flora.

CONCLUSION

The seed bank of *Acacia paradoxa* on Table Mountain is substantial but a good portion of it has been depleted by the 2009 fire. The remaining seed bank still pose a threat due to the high viability observed in these seeds, irrespective of age. While natural recruitment from seed is low due to low germinability attributed to high seed-coat imposed dormancy, this is enhanced when dormancy is broken by germination triggers of which heat is vital. Fire therefore could be a management option if the seed bank is to be depleted and eradication rendered feasible. The use of fire though should be coupled with not only a careful assessment of its potential negative impacts on native biodiversity but also with a comprehensive follow-up exercise meant to remove all recruited plants before they reproduce and multiply the current remnant seed bank. Removal of young plants will further allow native vegetation, whose density and species richness are negatively affected by that of *A. paradoxa*, to fully re-establish and minimize the risk of invasion and re-invasion. If allowed to survive, this fire could have set a stage for a leap in the extent of its invasion. The mutualism studied involve effective Rhizobia strains and have a significant positive impact on biomass accumulation, and height (growth); attributes that are documented as promoters of establishment and invasiveness. It remains to be further investigated how these attributes relate to competitive ability *A. paradoxa* in its distribution range and how this would link to its invasive status.

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